

ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICES OF OVER-THE-COUNTER MEDICATIONS USE AMONG STUDENTS OF TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL

Mr. Yashwanth H. V.^{*}, Mrs. Nagashree R.², Dr. Mahendra Kumar B. J.³, Dr. Renukaradhya Chitti⁴

^{1,2}M. Pharm, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Sri Adichunchanagiri College of Pharmacy, B.G. Nagara, Mandya-571448, Karnataka, INDIA.

³Professor and Head of Department, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Sri Adichunchanagiri College of Pharmacy, B.G. Nagara, Mandya-571448, Karnataka, INDIA.

⁴Professor, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Sri Adichunchanagiri College of Pharmacy, B.G. Nagara, Mandya-571448, Karnataka, INDIA.

Article Received on 29 Nov. 2025,

Article Revised on 20 Dec. 2025,

Article Published on 01 Jan. 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18103151>

*Corresponding Author

Mr. Yashwanth H. V.

M. Pharm, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Sri Adichunchanagiri College of Pharmacy, B.G. Nagara, Mandya-571448, Karnataka, India.

How to cite this Article: Mr. Yashwanth H. V.^{*}, Mrs. Nagashree R.², Dr. Mahendra Kumar B. J.³, Dr. Renukaradhya Chitti⁴. (2026). A ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICES OF OVER-THE-COUNTER MEDICATIONS USE AMONG STUDENTS OF TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(1), 492-503.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Over-the-counter (OTC) drugs are pharmaceuticals that can be bought straight from pharmacies or retailers. Self-medication can be dangerous because people may misdiagnose themselves, wait too long to get help from a doctor, take the wrong amount of medicine, have harmful side effects, combine drugs, or become addicted to them, which can hurt them mentally and physically. **Aim:** The aim of the study was to determine the prevalence, awareness, and practices regarding over-the-counter medicine usage among pharmacy, nursing, and natural science students at a tertiary care teaching hospital in Karnataka, India. **Method:** A prospective, cross-sectional questionnaire survey was conducted. IBM SPSS v27 and Chi-square tests were used to analyse data. **Results:** Among 200 participants, 81% of the respondents knew about OTC medicines and 83.5% of them expressed confidence in using them to treat common conditions. Over half (52%) said they self-medicated without seeing a doctor and pharmacy

students (65% most likely to do so) ($p = 0.010$). A significant percentage (71%) stored OTC medicines at home and 70.5% said they used them after being given advice by friends or relatives. Those who had experienced adverse effects were 30.5% and those who had taken more than the recommended dose were 11.5%. **Conclusion:** OTC medicine is used by a large number of health science students, where the pharmacy students are the most frequent users although they have higher academic exposures. Obtained results have revealed the significance of special educational activities and the involvement of pharmacists in the process of rational use guidance.

KEYWORDS: Over the counter medicine, self-medication, side effects, health science students.

INTRODUCTION

Over-the-counter (OTC) drugs are pharmaceuticals that can be bought straight from pharmacies or retailers. They are categorized by regulatory agencies according to their safety and effectiveness and are used to treat minor ailments like heartburn, headaches, the common cold, and allergies.^[1] The majority of nations have laws governing the use of over-the-counter medications and recognize them as a separate class of medication. At present, there are no licensing rules for over-the-counter medications in India. In India, OTC medications are not given a specific classification, and the majority of medications that do not fit into the prescription medication schedule are sold as OTC medications.^[2]

With the development in self-care and self-medication activities, the trend to deregulate more drugs with established safety and efficacy records to OTC status is also rising, and this rise is supported by policymakers, healthcare professionals (HCPs), consumers, and pharmaceutical companies. Self-medication using OTC drugs not only enables patients with increased autonomy to handle minor ailments but also benefits in cost economization of health care expenses.^[3] In the last few years, self-medication with OTC drugs has become more prevalent because of easy availability. This has direct implications for health science students who, as future healthcare professionals, have to advise patients about the benefits and dangers of self-medication. Health science students are likely to have a higher occurrence of self-medication than the general population because they are exposed to medical information.^[4]

Compared to older adults, young adults—who are mostly college-aged—are more likely to have injuries like musculoskeletal and back/spinal pain, and they may also have different

attitudes and views about how to address their pain.^[5] Notably, the percentage of students who self-medicated varied from 29% to 98.7%, whereas the percentage who used prescription medication was only 11.5%.^[6] Acetaminophen, ibuprofen, and aspirin are examples of over-the-counter pain relievers that carry risks such as incorrect self-diagnosis, inappropriate dosage, addiction, and adverse drug reactions. Careful use is essential because of its legal availability, affordability, and lack of age restrictions.^[7] Only 50% of patients read usage instructions, and only 20% use safety labels, even though there are over 300,000 over-the-counter medications available, including 80 therapeutic drug classes.^[8]

OTC drugs can be easily diverted for a number of reasons, including i) their widespread availability and ease of purchase, both online and in local stores; ii) their frequent low cost; and, lastly, iii) their legality and assumed innocuousness.^[9] Despite the fact that medications have many advantages, misuse can have major negative effects on one's health. Evidence continues to grow that adverse reactions to medications are a common, yet often preventable, cause of illness and even death.^[1]

Self-medication can be dangerous because people may misdiagnose themselves, wait too long to get help from a doctor, take the wrong amount of medicine, have harmful side effects, combine drugs, or become addicted to them, which can hurt them mentally and physically. So, you need a doctor's permission to take medication.^[10] Prescription and over-the-counter (OTC) medication abuse has been found to be a neglected problem that affects a variety of individuals who are at risk. However, based on data from the US National Surveys on Drug Use and Health, intentional abuse of both prescription and over-the-counter drugs has been gradually increasing.^[11]

The use of over-the-counter (OTC) medications in a misuse, abuse, or dependence pattern is underreported owing to inadequate sales monitoring and the favorable legal status of OTCs. There is, however, a "pharming" phenomenon owing to rising treatment admissions, hazardous behavior, emergency room admissions, deaths from drugs, and overdoses.^[12] A study found that 28% of the 178 recorded deaths were caused by over-the-counter medications. OTC medications are marketed in accordance with monograph standards that do not necessitate pre-market assessments of their contents, and they may contain excipients from prescription medications whose formulations differ from those approved by New Drug Applications (NDAs).^[13]

Since self-medication is still a major global health issue, several governmental organizations have implemented a number of laws and guidelines to curb the practice and raise awareness of medications. According to research, it's critical to ask pharmacy professionals for advice to ensure safe and efficient drug self-medication.^[14]

OBJECTIVES

Primary objectives

To access the medication-taking behaviour and prevalence of OTC medication among students in tertiary care teaching hospital.

Secondary objectives

- To provide knowledge on the administration of any OTC medicine.
- To identify any side effects associated with use of medicine.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Students studying pharmacy, nursing, and natural science at a tertiary care teaching hospital in Karnataka participated in a prospective, cross-sectional, observational questionnaire study. The purpose and objectives of the study was communicated to students, and written consent was acquired from every participant.

Part I of the questionnaire includes inquiries about demographic data; Part II: questions linked to attitude towards OTC pharmaceuticals and their practice (twelve questions) were distributed to all 200 students who agreed to take part, and then collected from students immediately after twenty minutes.

Ethical committee approval

The study has been conducted after the approval of the institutional ethics committee.

Statistical Analysis

The data obtained were analysed using IBM SPSS v27.

Table 1: Distribution of study subjects based on demographic details.

DEMOGRAPHIC DETAILS	FREQUENCY (N)	PERCENTAGE (%)
GENDER		
Female	132	66.0%
Male	68	34.0
AGE		

Above 20 years	161	80.5
Below 20 years	39	19.5
EDUCATIONAL STATUS		
Nursing	70	35.0
Natural science	70	35.0
Pharmacy	60	30.0

RESULTS

Total 200 subjects were enrolled in the study, of which 132 were female (66.0%) and 68 were male (34.0%). The subjects were categorized into age groups. Age groups above 20 years were in the majority, accounting for 161 (80.5%), and age groups below 20 years were minimal in number 39 (19.5%). Among subjects, 70 (35.0%) were nursing students, 70 (35.0%) were natural science students, and 60 (30.0%) were pharmacy students which is described as in table number 1.

Table 2: Awareness and knowledge of OTC medication use among college students.

Questions and responses	Total n =200(%)	Nursing n=70(%)	Natural science n=70(%)	Pharmacy n =60(%)	P value
Are you aware of over-the-counter (OTC) medications?					
Yes	81%	87.1%	81.4%	73.3%	0.134
No	19%	12.9%	18.6%	26.7%	
Do you feel confident in your ability to choose the right OTC medication for common ailments (e.g., headache, cold)?					
Yes	83.5%	92.9%	74.3%	83.3%	0.013
No	16.5%	7.1%	25.7%	16.7%	
Do you think it is important to consult a pharmacist before using a new medication?					
Yes	88%	88.6%	82.9%	93.3%	0.184
No	12%	11.8%	17.1%	6.7%	
Do you believe that OTC medications are safe to use without medical supervision?					
Yes	15%	5.7%	24.3%	16.7%	0.09
No	85%	94.3%	75.7%	83.3%	
Do you agree that non-prescription medicines can have dangerous side effects?					
Yes	85.5%	87.1%	80%	90%	0.242
No	14.5%	12.9%	20%	10%	
Do you think college students need more education about the safe use of OTC medications?					
Yes	100%	100%	100%	100%	-
No	-	-	-	-	

Table 2 compared survey responses across three educational groups—Natural Science, Nursing, and Pharmacy—analysing responses and assessing statistical significance. The

analysis revealed several statistically significant differences among the groups. Around 81% of students are aware of OTC medications, and 19% are not aware of it. No significant differences were observed as the p-values exceeded 0.05, indicating similar responses across educational groups. Nursing students (92.9%) feel more confident in their ability to choose the right OTC medications for common ailments compared to pharmacy (83.3%) and natural science (74.3%), which showed a significant difference with a p-value of 0.013. Over 88% of students think it is important to consult a pharmacist before using an OTC medication, and 12% think it's not important. Also, 85% of students believe that OTC medications are not safe to use without medical supervision, and 15% of them believe it's safe. 85.5% of participants agree that non-prescription medicines can have dangerous side effects, and 14.5% do not agree. No significant differences were observed, as the p-values exceeded 0.05. Notably, all participants in all three groups (100%) think college students need more education about the safe use of OTC medications.

Table 3: Patterns of drug usage among college students.

Questions and responses	Total <i>n</i> =200(%)	Nursing <i>n</i> =70(%)	Natural science <i>n</i> =70(%)	Pharmacy <i>n</i> =60(%)	P value
Do you usually read the label/instructions before using an OTC medication?					
Yes	84.5%	80%	87.1%	86.4%	0.445
No	15.5%	20%	12.9%	13.6%	
Do you frequently use OTC medication without consulting doctor?					
Yes	52%	54.3%	38.6%	65%	0.010
No	48%	45.7%	61.4%	35%	
Do you keep a stock of common OTC medication at home for immediate use?					
Yes	71%	67.1%	64.3%	83.3%	0.039
No	29%	32.9%	35.7%	16.7%	
Have you ever used an OTC medication based on a recommendation from a friend or family member?					
Yes	70.5%	64.3%	65.7%	83.3%	0.033
No	29.5%	35.7%	34.3%	16.7%	
Have you ever taken more than the recommended dose of an OTC medication?					
Yes	11.5%	7.1%	20%	6.7%	0.022
No	88.5%	92.9%	80%	93.3%	
Did you experience any adverse reactions or side effects during self-mediations?					
Yes	30.5%	30%	34.3%	26.7%	0.262
No	69.5%	70%	65.7%	73.3%	

Table 3 shows that over 84.5% usually read the label/instructions before using an OTC medication and 15.5% do not read; no significant differences were observed. Pharmacy students (65%) were found to be most frequently using OTC medication without consulting a

doctor compared to those in nursing (54.3%) and natural science (38.6%), with a significant p-value of 0.010. Most of the pharmacy students (83.3%) keep a stock of common OTC medication at home for immediate use compared to nursing (67.1%) and natural science (64.3%) ($p = 0.039$). A higher percentage of pharmacy participants (83.3%) used an OTC medication based on a recommendation from a friend or family member, compared to nursing (64.3%) and natural science (65.7%), with a significant p-value of 0.033. Most of the natural science students (20%) have taken more than the recommended dose of an OTC medication compared to those in nursing (7.1%) and pharmacy (6.7%), with a significant p-value of 0.022. Over 30.5% of participants experience adverse reactions or side effects during self-medication, and 69.5% do not. No significant differences were observed, as the p-values exceeded 0.05.

Table 4: Age groups comparison: Insights from questionnaire survey results.

Questions		Age groups		P value
		Under 20 years	Above 20 years	
Are you aware of over the counter (OTC) medications?	Yes	24 (61.5%)	138 (85.7%)	<0.001
	No	15 (38.5%)	23 (14.3%)	
Do you frequently use OTC medication without consulting a doctor?	Yes	23 (59%)	81 (50.3%)	0.331
	No	16 (41%)	80 (49.7%)	
Do you usually read the label/instructions before using an OTC medication?	Yes	30 (76.9%)	138 (86.3%)	0.150
	No	9 (23.1%)	22 (13.8%)	
Do you keep a stock of common OTC medication at home for immediate use?	Yes	25 (64.1%)	117 (72.7%)	0.290
	No	14 (35.9%)	44 (27.3%)	
Have you ever used OTC medication based on a recommendation from a friend or family member?	Yes	27 (69.2%)	114 (70.8%)	0.846
	No	12 (30.8%)	47 (29.2%)	
Do you feel confident in your ability to choose the right OTC medication for common ailments (ex: headache, cold)?	Yes	32 (82.1%)	135 (83.9%)	0.786
	No	7 (17.9%)	26 (16.1%)	
Do you think it is important to consult a pharmacist before using a new medication?	Yes	36 (92.3%)	140 (87%)	0.582
	No	3 (7.7%)	21 (13%)	
Do you believe that OTC medications are safe to use without medical supervision?	Yes	5 (12.8%)	25 (15.6%)	0.661
	No	34 (87.2%)	135 (84.4%)	
Have you ever taken more than the recommended dose of an OTC medication?	Yes	1 (2.6%)	22 (13.7%)	0.051
	No	38 (97.4%)	139 (86.3%)	
Did you experience any adverse reactions or Side effects during self-medication?	Yes	9 (23.1%)	52 (32.3%)	0.262
	No	30 (76.9%)	109 (67.7%)	
Do you agree that non-prescription medicines can have dangerous side effects?	Yes	31 (79.5%)	140 (87%)	0.235
	No	8 (20.5%)	21 (13%)	
Do you think college students need more education about the safe use of OTC medications?	Yes	132 (100%)	68 (100%)	-

The table 4 compares OTC medication use between college students under 20 and over 20 years, focusing on practice and attitudes. A higher percentage of students over 20 (85.7%) have heard of OTC medication than those under 20 (61.5%) ($P < 0.001$). Self-usage without doctor consultation is similar, with 59% of older students and 50.3% of younger students ($p = 0.331$). Older students read labels more frequently (86.3%) than younger students (76.9%) ($p = 0.150$). Confidence in selecting the right drug is similar for both groups, with over 80% in each ($p = 0.786$). Around 91% of both groups agree on consulting a pharmacist before using new medication ($p = 0.582$). Both groups have poor understanding of when it's safe to take OTC medications without medical supervision ($p = 0.661$). Notably, 13.7% of older students and 2.6% of younger students have taken more than the recommended dose ($p = 0.051$). Reporting adverse reactions was similar (32.3% vs. 23.1%, $p = 0.262$). Both groups agree that OTC drugs can have serious consequences (87% of older, 79.5% of younger students, $p = 0.235$), and all students believe more education on OTC medications is needed.

DISCUSSION

We need to have a good understanding of current attitudes and practices in order to change how the public views over-the-counter drugs. This study has intended to achieve that within a small sample of college students; among the 200 study participants, 70 are from nursing, 70 are from natural science, and 60 pharmacy students are participating.

Compared to pharmacy and nursing students, natural science students reported using over-the-counter medications less frequently. OTC drug consumption was highest among nursing students; among 64.3%, students used these drugs on a referral from a friend or family member. Additionally, a sizable portion of students studying natural science and pharmacy reported using recommendations from friends or relatives. When compared to those studying natural science, pharmacy students reported the lowest number of negative consequences. This discrepancy can result from pharmacy students' curriculum-based first-hand knowledge of medication prescriptions, usage, and side effects.

It shows that 30% of study participants with a history of self-medication have encountered side effects from over-the-counter drugs. Furthermore, 84% of people regularly read the directions on medication labels, whereas 16% never do. In contrast, **Kidist M et al.**, conducted a similar study among medical and pharmacy students at the University of Gondar, Gondar, Northwest Ethiopia. Of the 303 study participants with a history of SM, 263 (86.8%) reported experiencing side effects from over-the-counter medications. On the other hand, just

150 participants (39.5%) said they always read the directions on medication labels before using them, while 16 participants (4.2%) said they never did.^[1]

Among the 200 respondents, 81% of them are aware of OTC medication, and 83.5% of them feel confident in their ability to choose the right OTC medication for common ailments such as headaches and colds. Nursing students were found to have a larger percentage of high awareness compared to pharmacy students. This is in contrast to a comparable study conducted by **Sowmya K et al.**, among medical and paramedical students of an urban tertiary care hospital, Coimbatore Medical College, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India, where among 300 respondents, 49.7% of them knew the definition of the term “OTC drugs,” with 27.3% of them having recommended OTC drugs to others. It was discovered that while paramedical students had a higher percentage of poor awareness, medical students had a higher percentage of high awareness.^[15]

Over 52% of students frequently use OTC medication without consulting a doctor, and 71% of them keep a stock of common OTC medication at home for immediate use. We found that pharmacy students are using more OTC drugs compared to nursing and natural science students with enough knowledge. This is in contrast to a similar study conducted by **Pankajkumar M et al.**, 2nd year medical students of Belagavi Institute of Medical Sciences Belagavi, where 69.5% of students use medication without prescription, and analgesics (44.3%) are the highest OTC stocked at home, followed by antipyretics (35.2%), antihistamines (30.6%), antacids (18.1%), vitamins (18.1%), and antibiotics (12.5%).^[16]

CONCLUSION

The present research investigated the over-the-counter drug use among health science students of a tertiary care teaching hospital in Karnataka, India. It consisted of 200 pharmacy, nursing and natural science students. Based on the results, it is revealed that 81 percent of students have some knowledge of OTC drugs. The awareness results are higher among nursing students at 87.1%, whereas 83.5 percent of students are certain that they can choose the correct OTC medications to treat such conditions as headaches and colds. Nevertheless, 52 percent of them tend to manage on their own by self-medicating without even approaching a doctor. Students of pharmacy, most of them being 65%, are the most prone to self-medicate their diseases and statistics indicate that 71 percent of them keep over-the-counter medication in their homes demonstrating accessibility and dependence.

Moreover, 84.5 percent of the students read the labels and 30.5 percent admitted that they were emotionally affected by such medications. In addition, 11.5 percent disclosed that they had exceeded the recommended dose and the highest rate was observed with natural science students at 20 percent.

The issue of age is also a factor. Older students (85.7%) are more conscious of OTC drugs as compared to younger students (61.5), though both, most of them practice self-medication. Further, 85 percent are aware of dangers of OTC medications misuse and all tend to believe that there should be greater education. These results indicate that demographic factors like age, gender, and education have effects on the use of OTC drugs, and this can be the cause of unsafe practices. So, effective classes in schools and college and motivating talk with pharmacists will be necessary to make people safer, decrease poor outcomes, and teach future medical professionals to engage responsibly in self-medication.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The writers are extremely grateful to the principal and the faculty of Shri Adichuchanagiri College of Pharmacy for all of the support and guidance they gave them when they were composing this evaluation.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST: None.

FUNDING: Not Applicable.

REFERENCES

1. Bekele KM, Abay AM, Mengistu KA, Atsbeha BW, Demeke CA, Belay WS, et al. Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice on Over-the-Counter Drugs Among Pharmacy and Medical Students: A Facility-Based Cross-Sectional Study. *Integr Pharm Res Pract.*, Sept. 2020; 9: 135–46.
2. Marathe P, Kamat S, Tripathi R, Raut S, Khatri N. Over-the-counter medicines: Global perspective and Indian scenario. *J Postgrad Med.*, Jan. 2020; 66(1): 28–34.
3. Narang P, Garg V, Sharma A. Regulatory, safety and economic considerations of over-the-counter medicines in the Indian population. *Discov Health Syst*, May 22, 2023; 2(1): 17.
4. Khadka S, Kc R, Luitel A, Thapa Chhetri S, Gurung S, Panta PP, et al. Understanding and practices of over-the-counter drugs for self-care among students of different medical

- faculties in a low-and middle-income country. *Ann Med Surg*, May 2025; 87(5): 2615–25.
5. Attitudes and Beliefs of College Students towards Pain Management Modalities: Theory of Planned Behavior Approach. *Chronic Pain Manag* [Internet], 2022 Nov 21 [cited 2025 Dec 3]; 6(1). Available from: <https://www.gavinpublishers.com/article/view/attitudes-and-beliefs-of-college-students-towards-pain--management-modalities-theory-of-planned-behavior-approach>
 6. Alenzi EO, Bedaiwi SKA, Hamayun R, Alanazi AST, Fawzy MS. Key modifiable risk factors for self-medication among university students: An observational study. *Explor Res Clin Soc Pharm.*, Sept. 2024; 15: 100483.
 7. Rajab MH, Ewis SK, Almatar K, Abdelmajed LY, Ba Sowid MS, Bajaber MO, et al. Utilization of Over-the-Counter Painkillers Among Medical Students During Academic Examinations. *Cureus* [Internet]. 2023 Aug 18 [cited 2025 Dec 3]; Available from: <https://www.cureus.com/articles/166012-utilization-of-over-the-counter-painkillers-among-medical-students-during-academic-examinations>
 8. Rude TA, Eukel HN, Ahmed-Sarwar N, Burke ES, Anderson AN, Riskin J, et al. An Introductory Over-the-Counter Simulation for First-Year Pharmacy Students Using a Virtual Pharmacy. *Am J Pharm Educ.*, Mar. 2023; 87(2): ajpe8940.
 9. Chiappini S, Ceci F, Mosca A, Di Carlo F, Burkauskas J, Pettorruso M, et al. Knowledge and Use of Over-the-counter Drugs in Italy: An Exploratory Survey-based Study in the General Population. *Curr Neuropharmacol*, Jan. 2023; 21(1): 133–41.
 10. Honnekeri A, Bhavshaikh N, Shah M, Nayak U. Self-medication in medical students in urban India: Exploring the extent of this dangerous practice. *J Fam Med Prim Care*, Aug. 2024; 13(8): 3381–7.
 11. Chiappini S, Schifano F. What about “Pharming”? Issues Regarding the Misuse of Prescription and Over-the-Counter Drugs. *Brain Sci.*, Oct. 14, 2020; 10(10): 736.
 12. Schifano F, Chiappini S, Miuli A, Mosca A, Santovito MC, Corkery JM, et al. Focus on Over-the-Counter Drugs’ Misuse: A Systematic Review on Antihistamines, Cough Medicines, and Decongestants. *Front Psychiatry*, May 7, 2021; 12: 657397.
 13. Diantini A, Alfaqeeh M, Permatasari L, Nurfitriani M, Durotulailah L, Wulandari W, et al. Clinical Toxicology of OTC Cough and Cold Pediatric Medications: A Narrative Review. *Pediatr Health Med Ther.*, July 15, 2024: 243–55.

14. Al-Kubaisi KA, R. Abduelkarem A, M Hassanein M. Prevalence and associated risk factors of self-medication with over-the-counter medicines among university students in the United Arab Emirates. *Pharm Pract*, Sept. 23, 2022; 20(3): 01–6.
15. K S, P S. Knowledge, attitudes, and practices of over-the-counter drug usage among medical and paramedical students of an urban tertiary care hospital. *Natl J Physiol Pharm Pharmacol*, 2021; 11(6): 1.
16. Hiremath G, Hiremath S, Omkar P. A study on use of over-the-counter drugs among 2nd year medical students - A cross-sectional study. *Natl J Physiol Pharm Pharmacol*, 2022; 12(1): 1.